

Effect of different P levels on grain yield of rice under flash flooding (submerged) and natural intermediate deep water conditions (unsubmerged), Cuttack, India.

P level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)								
	1987 (Direct effect)			1988 (Cumulative effect)			1989 (Residual effect)		
	Submerged	Unsubmerged	Mean	Submerged	Unsubmerged	Mean	Submerged	Unsubmerged	Mean
0	2.3	5.2	3.7	0.8	2.7	1.8	2.6	3.3	2.8
8.8	3.1	5.2	4.1	2.4	3.3	2.9	3.3	3.5	3.4
17.6	3.4	5.1	4.3	2.3	3.4	2.9	3.2	3.6	3.4
26.4	3.2	5.3	4.3	2.4	3.7	3.1	3.3	3.6	3.4
35.2	3.2	5.1	4.2	2.7	3.8	3.3	3.3	3.6	3.5
Mean	3.0	5.2		2.1	3.4		3.1	3.5	
LSD (0.05)									
Submergence levels		0.9			0.7			0.6	
P levels		0.3			0.4			0.2	
(Interaction)		0.5			ns			ns	

was more in 1987 (2.2 t/ha) and 1988 (1.3 t/ha) than in 1989 (0.4 t/ha) because of the varying depth and duration of crop submergence (see table). P proved beneficial when the crop was subjected to flash flooding or when it was grown in the same plots and could take advantage of residual P effects.

The interaction between submergence and P levels was significant in 1987 but

not in 1988 and 1989. P fertilizer up to 17.6 kg P/ha in 1987 increased grain yield under submerged conditions but not under unsubmerged conditions. Effect of P was observed under both conditions in 1988, though it was more pronounced under submerged than unsubmerged condition, possibly due to the cumulative effect of P. Grain yield increased significantly under both conditions in

1989, thus confirming the residual effect of P, though effects of 20-80 kg P/ha treatments were similar.

Results indicate that fertilizing with 8.8-17.6 kg P/ha is essential for DWR submerged by flash flooding at the early vegetative stage. Residual effects of P under excess water situations need consideration when calculating P fertilizer doses on a long-term basis. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Leaf blast (Bl)-leaffolder (LF) interactions in lowland rice

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The individual and combined development of Bl (*Pyricularia grisea*) and LF (*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*) were measured in glasshouse experiments as Bl severity and LF consumption during Aug 1990-Mar 1991 using direct seeded IR72 in plastic trays under lowland conditions. Treatments of an uninoculated check, single Bl inoculation, single LF infestation, and combinations of subsequent LF infestation at 7 d after Bl inoculation (Bl-LF), subsequent Bl inoculation at 7 d after LF infestation (LF-BI), and subsequent LF infestation after Bl inoculation within 24 h (Bl-LF [24 h]) were applied at 20 and 40 d after sowing (DAS) using randomized complete block design with three replications.

An inoculum suspension of isolate PO6-6 containing 100,000 spores/ml was sprayed onto plants with an atomizer attached to a vacuum pump. Inoculation

1. Diseased and consumed leaf area of IR72 in trials at 20 and 40 DAS.

Diseased leaf area (%)

Consumed leaf area (%)

Total damaged area (%)

was inside a wooden chamber lined with wet jute sacks and covered with plastic sheets.

Two 2d-instar LF larvae were placed on the youngest leaf of each plant using a wet fine camel's hair brush. Each seedling was then enclosed in a mylar cage with nylon mesh on top.

Diseased leaf area (DLA) and consumed leaf area (CLA) were traced on clear acetate plastic sheets and run through a leaf area meter (LICOR, model LI-3000) for four consecutive weekly samplings after treatment application. Total damaged area was determined by adding DLA and CLA.

Reduced DLA showed that LF consumption had an antagonistic effect on BI development in the trials at 20 and 40 DAS (Fig. 1). DLA in the LF-BI treatment was significantly lower than in the single BI inoculation treatment in the 20 DAS trial. In the 40 DAS trial, the LF-BI treatment produced significantly lower DLA relative to the other treatments. BI inoculation at 7 d after LF infestation appears to slow BI development at pest infestation times of 20 and 40 DAS (Fig. 1).

An antagonistic effect between BI and LF was observed in CLA in the 20 DAS trial where the combination treatments of LF-BI and BI-LF (24 h) showed significantly lower CLA than the single LF infestation treatment at 34, 41, and 48 DAS. BI-LF combination treatment, however, produced a significantly higher CLA than the single LF infestation treatment at 54, 61, and 68 DAS in the 40 DAS trial. This suggests that BI development might have a synergistic effect on LF consumption at 40 DAS, when LF infestation starts at 7 d after BI inoculation (Fig. 1).

Total damaged area showed a less than additive interaction between BI and

LF in the 20 DAS trial. Total damaged areas in the combination treatments were significantly lower than in the summed single BI and LF treatments (Fig. 2).

In the 40 DAS trial, no significant differences were observed for total damaged areas among combination treatments of BI-LF and BI-LF (24 h) and the summed single BI and LF treatments. However, the LF-BI combination treatment produced a significantly lower total damaged area compared with the other combination treatments and added single BI and LF treatments. This implies

2. Total damaged area of IR72 in trials at 20 and 40 DAS.

an antagonistic interaction of LF and BI when BI was inoculated at 7 d after LF infestation (Fig. 2).

Our results show that at 20 DAS, BI and LF interact antagonistically, in which BI decreases LF consumption. In addition, LF consumption decreases DLA when BI is inoculated at 7 d after LF infestation. At 40 DAS, LF consumption antagonizes BI development when BI is inoculated at 7 d after LF infestation, while a synergistic effect of BI on LF consumption occurs when LF infestation starts at 7 d after BI inoculation. ■

Seed dry-heat treatment against transmission of *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae*, causal agent of bacterial sheath brown rot of rice (BSR)

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BSR is a major constraint to growing rice in Burundi's swamps at elevations of more than 1,300 m. BSR is transmitted on seed.

Effect of seed age on ability to germinate before and after heat treatment (6 d at 65 ± 1 °C) for Yunnan 3. Burundi, 1992.^a

Seed harvest	Germination rate (%)	
	Before treatment	After treatment
May 1992	90 ± 2	79 ± 8
Jun 1991	51 ± 7	1 ± 2
May 1991	47 ± 9	3 ± 3
Jun 1990	3 ± 3	0 ± 0
Jun 1989	0 ± 0	-

^aMean of 5 × 20 seeds.

Decrease of viability during dry heat treatment (65 ± 1 °C). Each point was obtained from 5 × 20 seeds.

Germination rate (%)

